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THE IMPORTANCE OF REALIA IN TRANSLATION STUDY

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Annotation: It is clear that each nation and country has its unique culture and background including special or local words, phrases that are not translated directly into other languages and that makes us address realia.

Key words: language, culture, linguoculturology, realia, local words, special phrases.

A language and culture often come together and by translating written literary texts, poems, novels and works from one language into another, one can be aware of this or that nation or country. There are numerous terms in the culture of nations that are translated into other languages directly or need to be replaced with other words but in some cases, they are not translated and remain as their real versions as they have no equivalent words in those languages. Studying this kind of issues is a problem of both linguoculturology and the translation study. As a result, one who is working on this, has to address the term “*realia*” without what, it is quite impossible to translate texts, poems, works of literature within languages, having various culture and word expressions. Because each nation, culture and country has words, phrases or idioms that cannot be translated directly into other languages due to the missing equivalents of those words which make them leave without being translated.

Realia is a cultural-specific word or word expressions that refers local word or phrase which cannot be translated into other languages directly as they have no obvious equivalent in the given languages.

One of the well-known Uzbek novels, "O'tkan kunlar" ("Days gone by") is a good example which is rich in national Uzbek words and phrases and while translating them, from Uzbek into Russian, translators and even readers, reading the translated version of the novel may come across **realia**.

For instance, in Russian version of the novel "O'tkan Kunlar" ("Минувшие дни") there is a sentence:

- "“Странно,странно!”- пробормотал он,закладывая под язык щепотку **наса**” which means: “Strange, strange” he muttered, putting a pinch of “**nas**”(is a special type of tobacco, which is placed under the tongue)under his tongue”.

Actually, the word is called “**nos**” in Uzbek and especially popular with the old men who are addicted to it and use that as a type of tobacco by putting under their tongues. Another given word “**kurpacha**” is special for central Asian countries and used in the novel “O'tkan Kunlar”((“Минувшие дни”) and translated into Russian like:”Дай ей вон те новые **курпачи**,пусть ими накроет **санда**л,meaning: “let her cover **sandal** with **kurpachi**.” In fact, the word **kurpa**(a smaller one, **kurpacha**) is a smaller blanket, sewn from national fabric which is used to lay on the floor to sit or lie on and **sandal** is a local heating item which has been used since ancient times in Central Asia, Afghanistan, Iran, Turkey, Japan and other Eastern countries and it is made by digging a hole at one end of the room, and the inside is treated in a special way and watered. A chair is installed on it and covered with a **kurpacha**.

It is evident that the words “**nos**”, “**kurpacha**”, “**sandal**” are cultural-special words that are mostly used by Eastern people rather than western ones. Thus, we cannot translate them directly into another language as there are no equivalent words for them.

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LINGUOCULTURAL FEATURES OF PARENT - CHILD SPEECH IN UZBEK AND ENGLISH LITERATURE

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Annotation. This thesis deals with cultural features of parent and child speech in English literary texts and the problems of translation of these features to Uzbek language. A person's relatives, whether they are near or distant, have a certain thing his place in life. Kinship can be divided into blood relatives and relatives according to the degree of closeness. In this study, we aimed to do a comparative analysis of the relations between this type of relatives in the English and Uzbek languages. Family, families and kinship relations form the culture of the people and show its specific characteristics, and help to realize the national, linguistic image of the world on a large scale. The issue of family relations applies not only to sociology, but also to cultural and linguistic studies. It is natural to approach this problem from the point of view of linguistic and cultural studies. Linguistic units with a cultural-national character attract the attention of researchers with the study of linguistics. Translating literary texts, however, is not an easy task because it

certainly poses many problems for the translator who should be bilingual and bicultural if needed.

Key words: Linguocultural features, parent-child speech, linguistic culture

Approaches to the study of parent-child relationships are made from different perspectives, such as psychiatry and psychology. Sociologists, psychologists, sociolinguists and linguists for many years. Based on literary texts, mass communication publications, poems, Lavitsky describes the concept of “Children” of the Vitebsk region of Belarus in his scientific article. It explores children's lives from different perspectives, in which the role and place of parents is inevitable. Go Pintin approaches this issue as a family tradition, comparing Chinese and Russian parentchild relationships based on proverbs and sayings of the two languages. Biktagirova makes a comparative analysis of the issue of the concept of “Family” based on the materials of different languages systematically, such as English, Turkish and other languages. The diversity of languages, the variety of cultures and necessity of communications in human life caused translation to be a very effective factor in communicating, exchanging cultures, and knowledge.⁶¹ A number of studies have specifically addressed the importance of a parent - child relationship in the family. Despite the love of parents, they need to develop the skills of communicating with children and listening to them. The diversity of languages, the variety of cultures and necessity of communications in human life caused translation to be a very effective factor in communicating, exchanging cultures, and knowledge.⁶²

For children, the family is one of the main places of residence, development and psychological formation. It is a family that creates relationships between family members. Parents are the main sources of interpersonal development for their children (parent-child relationships, parent-ancestor relationships). This issue has attracted attention the attention of many scientists. So what is the relationship

⁶¹ Bush, P. (1998) “Literary Translation.” In: M. Baker, ed. Routledge Encyclopedia of Translation Studies, London: Routledge

⁶² Chaal, Houaria.(2018). The cultural Constraints in Literary work. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press

between parents and children? The relationship between parents and children is explained by Dunn and Brown.⁶³ As they noted, this form of relationship allows the child to understand emotions, because in the conversation when a small child tells his parents about various situations, stories full of joy, surprise and other emotions, emotional speech between parents and children is inevitable. Another scientist says that a sincere conversation in the parent-child relationship guarantees respect, trust and security for the child's psychology.

For many years, in Uzbek culture even in the marriage of a son, obtaining the consent of the father, a marriage without the consent of the father or a white blessing is not a happy marriage.⁶⁴ To be degraded or to be disgraced among the people, and for this reason to marry a son or a daughter to marry a family of prospective brides-to-be. In the work of Abdulla Kadiri called "Last days" there were given statements which reflect the role of father in a family such as "Does the father rule in the family?" or "Does the father take care of everything in the family?" It has become a habit to be questioned with words like "Son, whether you hear it or not, we are a scapegoat for you we have done work". In this expression, we can understand from the words of Yusufbek Hoji, Otabek's father, that the most important thing in the family is the father saying, because the son does not double the word of the father, the father marries his son from the family he considers worthy. At this point, we can observe that the situation is completely different in English families, where a boy or a girl in the family can get married whenever and whoever they want. In English families, too, fathers try to raise their children well, pay special attention to their talents or abilities, and try to take their place in society according to their talents or abilities.

Communication depends on two interlocutors and under no circumstances should Hisham Altalib, Abdul Hamid Abu Sulaiman and Omar Altalib be interrupted. Relationship quality largely depends on parent-child communication,

⁶³ Dunn and Brown (1998), *Meaning based-translation: Guide to cross-language equivalence*, University of Richmond, Virginia

⁶⁴ N. Brooks, (1968), *Cultural features in the literary work*. In JM Valdes *Culture bound: bridging the cultural gap in language teaching*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press

parental feelings of burden Moore, Christine and Busby, Andrea and Bundy, Tawana.⁶⁵ Another group of scientists supports the idea that the earlier the parent-child relationship is formed, the more successful the relationship is established, because communication is related to emotional survival, understanding feelings.

However, parents differ in the extent to which they discuss feelings with their children. Insecure parents versus secure parents may feel more comfortable discussing positive and negative emotions with their children, and as a result, children of secure parents may have more opportunities to discuss and reflect on feelings. Although most of the work on predicting children's emotion understanding has focused on both parental characteristics such as depression.

In conclusion we can say that the parent-child relationship is culturally specific and reflected in the linguistic representation of the world mainly in proverbs. Examining the different manifestations of parent-child relationships in English and Uzbek cultures showed that cultural factors play an important role in this matter.

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